

TRACER STUDY OF THE BACHELOR OF ELEMENTARY EDUCATION IN TAGOLOAN COMMUNITY COLLEGE GRADUATES OF THE SCHOOL YEAR 2020-2021

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Abstract

The study assesses the present status and outcomes of the graduates of the Bachelor of Elementary Education batch 2020–2021 to gain insights into their current status, such as their eligibility and job status, and overall career development. The study employed a mixed-methods research design, combining surveys and interviews, to collect data from batch 2020-2021 graduates. The findings of this study revealed valuable insights into the status of the graduates. The researchers found that out of the 79 graduates, there were 48 identified to be eligible. The study also highlighted the challenges faced by the graduates when applying to institutions, in which they have encountered some major difficulties such as eligibility, experience, and finances. Furthermore, the study identified areas for improvement in terms of career support services, industry connections, and curriculum alignment.

Keywords: *Tracer, Elementary Education, Employment, Sustainability*

Introduction

Higher Educational Institutions play a vital role in the creation of professionals to address the high demands of the job market. Curriculum and graduate settlement are specific areas of concern as these are essential markers for a successful tertiary program.

According to Cahapay. (2020), higher education institutions continually deal with pressures coming from different directions. This condition often raises a concern about the responsiveness of their curriculum programs. The main reasons for unemployment can be both low job market demands and the graduates lack of experience (Abas et. al, 2022). For teachers having a degree in education and a license for teaching are just on one of the basic requirements (Almejas et. al, 2022), not mention the policies and standards set by the Philippine Professional Regulatory Commission. This ensures that teachers have met the educational requirements and have the necessary knowledge and skills to teach effectively. This implies that the graduates need to meet both the basic and required standards (Guanan et. al, 2022).

Tracer study helps academic administrators to assess the effectiveness of the program being offered. According to Cornillez, et. al. (2021) the primary reason teacher education graduates pursued teacher education degrees in college was the influence of their parents and relatives who convinced them to choose the programs they were likely to be employed in the job market after earning their teacher education degrees in college. However, it was revealed that the graduates' strong passion for the teaching profession was their main reason for earning teacher education degrees in college (Pentang, 2022).

The study was anchored by the neoclassical Keynesian Theory (2019), which explains unemployment as a temporary problem and as a result of inflation. Reduction in inflation would stabilize the economy, which in turn would lead to economic growth, and the reduction in unemployment is strongly empirically evident of the inverse relationship between unemployment and educational level which means that the rise in educational level will likely decrease unemployment rates (Weber, 2019).

In conclusion, a tracer study provides valuable information for the college institute to enhance its programs, strengthen industry partnerships, and improve career services for future graduates. The findings also contribute to a broader understanding of graduate outcomes and the effectiveness of higher education in preparing students for the job market. This study underscores the importance of continuous evaluation and improvement to ensure the relevance and success of Tagoloan Community College.

Methods

This research study particularly employed the use of Mixed Method Research – Explanatory Sequential design using two phases of data collection. The first phase was Quantitative data collection using questionnaires and then followed by Qualitative data collection and analysis through interviews and observation as the second phase. To test or generalize the results, mixed methods research which combines Quantitative and Qualitative approaches.

The researchers utilized Google Form as a way to gather the data. To do this, the researchers asked for the list of graduates of the Bachelor of Elementary Education batch 2020–2021 from the registrar's office through a letter request signed by the school administrators. The researcher traced the Bachelor of Elementary Education graduates of the school year 2020 up to 2021. The researchers will reach out and interview them via messenger, text, and call or by sending them an email, responses were then gathered analyzed using thematic analysis. The researchers chose the online platform to reach out to them. The study was conducted in the second semester of the academic year 2022-2023.

Results and Discussions

The data collected from the participants has revealed the different employment status of the Bachelor of Elementary Education graduates' batch 2020-2021.

Problem 1. What is the profile of the respondents?

The profile of the Bachelor of Elementary Education graduates from the school year 2020-2021, in terms of age group, gender, civil status, eligibility, and higher educational attainment. The overall response of the participants in terms of age group, the participants were found to be 26 years old or 33%, and in terms of gender, the participants were female 65 or 82%, and the male had only 14 or 18%, and in terms of civil status, data revealed that 48 of the participants or 61% are single, while 31 or 39% are married. The male and female teachers may bring different perspectives, teaching styles, and approaches to the classroom (Albina et. al, 2021).

In eligibility, the respondents were found to passed the licensure examination for teachers (LET) with exactly 48 or 61% were licensed teachers and in terms of higher educational attainment it was found out that majority of the respondents were still under the Bachelor's degree level which was 78 of the respondents or 99% and only one or 1% had MA units, then the rest such as MA, Doctorate Units, and Doctorate are not yet achieved. To clarify, all the 79 respondents have their Bachelor's Degrees and only one of them had taken the time to take MA units. Eligibility is requirement for educators to become professional teachers and to teach in public schools (Catacutan et. al, 2020).

Problem 2. What is the present status of the TCC BEED graduates S.Y. 2020 – 2021 in terms of employment, job status, seminars and training, and job description?

The overall response of the respondents in terms of employment status revealed that 72 or 91% of the graduates were employed. In terms of job status, 8 or 10% of the respondents are currently employed in a private institution, and there are only 3 or 4 are currently employed in Dep-Ed, then there are 68 or 86% of the participants are non-teaching. Teacher's major requirements are a bachelor's degree and a license to teach (Pentang et al. 2022). The researchers found possible factors that may influence the career choice of Bachelor of Elementary Education graduates such as personal interests and passions.

In terms of seminars and training, there are 5 or 6% institutional sponsored seminars and training and 7 or 9% personal cost seminars and training, then 67 or 85% of the respondents had no seminars and training. The researchers found that COVID-19 is the main possible factor that affects the training status of Bachelor of Elementary Education graduates. For their job descriptions, and of the respondents 11 or 14% of the respondents have a permanent job, and there are 7 or 9% are casuals, 56 or 71% are contractual, then there are 5 or 6% of the participants are job order. Concerning the employment status of the graduates, out of 79 respondents, there were 7 who were unemployed or casual employees.

Problem 3. What are the challenges encountered by the BEED graduates S.Y. 2020 – 2021?

Based on the results gathered from the researchers, there are two major problems that the graduates encountered specifically when they were looking for employment—it is the social economic challenges and employment experiences. These include financial difficulties, eligibility, job opportunities, and employment standards. One of the social challenges faced by graduates is financial difficulties which can be a significant factor that affects the graduate's present status. According to one of our respondents,

“No money, this makes me stressed and almost depressed, as we know that if have no money, we cannot support our needs and the requirements of the job market” (p1,p3,p7,p9,p12).

Furthermore, eligibility is also one of the social challenges that Bachelor of Elementary Education graduates have encountered in connection with financial incapability, it is difficult to have eligibility without financial support. It also revealed that, when it comes to job opportunities, one of the factors is not having enough experience. Eligibility, experience, and training enhance the skills and talents of the graduates (Gomez, 2023). Based also on the findings gathered by the researchers, employment standards are one of the major problems of graduates when seeking employment, they often encounter expectations and standards such as requirements for work experience, specific skills, and academic achievements.

Problem 4, What programs can be designed to address the challenges encountered by the Bachelor Eligibility Education graduates of the School Year 2020–2021?

By using Crisswell’s (2009) approach to tabulate data, the researchers have gathered two major recommendations such as institutional training and broader experiences programs. Institutional training holds significant importance in preparing graduates for their teaching careers, without adequate training, graduates may struggle to find employment in competitive job markets. Institutional Training equips Bachelor of Elementary Education Graduates with essential pedagogical knowledge and skills. They learn about different teaching methods, instructional strategies, and assessment techniques that are crucial for effective teaching and student engagement (Gomez, 2023). For the Broader Experiences, it allows graduates to apply their knowledge and skills in real-world settings. The experiences of the graduates dictate their training and enhance their skills and talents.

Conclusion

The Tagoloan Community College Bachelor of Elementary Education graduates who participated in this study were composed of single females who fell within the age range of 31 to 35 years of age. The Bachelor of Elementary Education graduates were eligible in terms of the Licensure Examination for Teachers, furthermore in terms of highest educational attainment the participants were found bachelor’s degree holders as it is the minimum requirement for many job opportunities. The Bachelor of Elementary Education graduates were found contractually employed, and those who were currently unemployed perceived that there was no job opportunity as the main reason for their unemployment.

Based on the results and discussions obtained in the study, the participants were found employed in non-teaching, and out of 79 graduates there were only 3 of them were in Dep-Ed and the other 8 of them were in private institutions. The graduates were unable to undergo seminars and training, out of 79 graduates there were only 5 of them had taken the institutional sponsored seminars, and there were also 7 of them were able to have personal cost seminars and training. The Bachelor of Elementary Education graduates stated that they have encountered problems when they were looking for employment such as financial difficulties and eligibility as it is one of the major standards or requirements for teachers.

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